

Unveiling the Mediating Role of Leadership Skills in the Link between Cultural Intelligence and Conflict Management Styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa

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Abstract

The study aimed to identify the mediation role of leadership skills in the relationship between cultural intelligence and Lupong Tagapamayapa's conflict management styles in Malita, Davao Occidental. It also attempted to identify the important correlations between the factors and ascertain how leadership abilities mediate the relationship between cultural intelligence and lupong tagapamayapa's conflict resolution techniques. The work employed a descriptive-correlational research design. In all, the survey included 180 respondents from lupong tagapamayapa in every barangay in Malita, Davao Occidental. The independent variable was assessed using an adapted version of the "Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) Questionnaire" from Van Dyne et al. (2015), the dependent variable using the Reginald (2006) "Conflict Management Styles", and the leadership skills survey questionnaire from McLaughlin et al. (2020) to quantify the mediating factor. The statistical methods applied were Medgraph employing Sobel Z-Test, Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation Analysis, and Mean and Standard Deviation.

Keywords: *Leadership Skills, Cultural Intelligence, Conflict Management Styles, Lupong Tagapamayapa, Descriptive-Correlational, Mediating Effect, Philippines*

RATIONALE

Divergent interests, values, and views can cause conflict. Conflict can arise at various levels, including interpersonal disputes, organizational conflicts, and international conflicts. Conflict resolution methods, including communication, negotiation, and mediation, aim to satisfy all parties (Perbawa, 2022). Global organizations perceive the need to equip professionals with diverse conflict management styles, recognizing that it's an unavoidable issue (Bao et al., 2016). Thus, conflicts can arise at any time, and the way to employ conflict management methods depends on one's conflict management style and abilities (Kathiravan & Rajasekar, 2018). Despite the never-ending presence of conflict and violence, the Philippines has a long history of conflict resolution, particularly in barangay settings. Thus, by virtue of Presidential Decree No. 1508, also known as the Katarungang Pambarangay Law, which was repealed by Republic Act 7160, otherwise known as the Local Government Code of 1991, the barangay justice system was officially established in 1979 to settle local disputes through and with lupong tagapamayapa (Gonzales, 2022). Thus, in accordance with the barangay justice system, Lupong Tagapamayapa had been active and performing its duties in the local governments of the Philippines for more than a decade (Augustin et al., 2018). And this organized administrative body can bring the parties in dispute together to resolve issues as much as possible (Jumalon et al., 2018).

Meanwhile, diverse global workplaces have created the need for culturally competent leaders (Brannen, 2016). Researchers view their cultural intelligence as a predictor of conflict management styles (Gonçalves et al., 2016). As well as their leadership skills that promote communication on both sides, they have been seen to contribute a great deal to positive outcomes in the workplace, in group collaborations, and in team environments (Kelly & MacDonald, 2019). Moreover, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, there was no other study that has investigated the same type of mediation scheme focusing on the three variables mentioned above. Thus, the absence of related studies and literature exploring the mediating effect of leadership skills on the relation of cultural intelligence and conflict management styles of lupong tagapamayapa, who are recognized in the Philippines for their work advancing the goals of the Katarungang Pambarangay (KP) under R.A. 7160 or the barangay justice system in their communities, had created a knowledge and literature gap among local researcher. Thus, the goal of the proposed study was to address the gap by aiming to determine the mediating effect of leadership skills on the relation of cultural intelligence and conflict management styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa in Malita

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of leadership skills on the relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa in Malita, Davao Occidental. Furthermore, the study was conducted in order to:

1. Determine the level of cultural intelligence of lupong tagapamayapa in Malita in terms of:
 - 1.1 Metacognitive;
 - 1.2 Cognitive;
 - 1.3 Motivational; and
 - 1.4 Behavioral.
2. Determine the level of conflict management styles of lupong tagapamayapa in Malita in terms of:
 - 2.1 Collaborating;
 - 2.2 Competing;
 - 2.3 Avoiding;
 - 2.4 Accommodating; and
 - 2.5 Compromising.
3. Determine the level of leadership skills among lupong tagapamayapa in Malita in terms of:
 - 3.1 Administrative skills;
 - 3.2 Interpersonal skills; and
 - 3.3 Conceptual skills.
4. Ascertain the significant relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles.
5. Ascertain the significant relationship between cultural intelligence and leadership skills.

6. Ascertain the significant relationship between leadership skills and conflict management styles.
7. Determine the mediating effect of leadership skills on the relation of cultural intelligence and conflict management styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa in Malita, Davao Occidental.

Hypotheses:

The null hypotheses in this study were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between cultural intelligence and leadership skills.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between leadership skills and conflict management styles.

Ho4: There is no mediating effect of leadership skills on the relation of cultural intelligence and conflict management styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa in Malita, Davao Occidental.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter included relevant articles and the results of prior studies undertaken on the subject by different authors. Their research encompassed data on cultural intelligence, conflict management methods, and the effectiveness of leadership skills. This chapter presents a review of relevant studies that examine the relationship between leadership qualities, cultural intelligence, and conflict management styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa. It also investigates if there is a substantial correlation among these three factors.

Cultural Intelligence

This section of the study discusses the independent variable, cultural intelligence, which spans the domains of metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral. Cultural intelligence contains four factors: metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral (Ang & Van Dyne, 2015). Since cultural connectivity is a prominent feature of people's lives, cultural intelligence can be defined as the ability to function in a diverse cultural context (Thomas & Van Dyne, 2018). Cultural intelligence emphasizes a person's potential for success in a wide range of cross-cultural situations and enhances a person's capacity for rapid cultural adaptation (Afsar et al., 2019).

Findings from Sanli Kayran and Unur (2022) showed that cultural intelligence has a positive effect on conflict management as well as a negative effect on forcing, avoiding, and career satisfaction. They also stated that cultural ability has a positive and negative effect on avoidance and conflict management.

Furthermore, cultural metacognition has a positive effect on compromising, yielding, problem-solving, avoiding, and career satisfaction. Akhal and Liu (2019) recently studied how cultural intelligence influences the adjustment and turnover intentions of expatriates in mainland China. They said that all three aspects of expatriates' cross-cultural adaptation could benefit from putting more emphasis on cultural intelligence. Similarly, Guðmundsdóttir (2015) found that cultural intelligence helps Nordic leaders adapt cross-culturally.

Metacognitive

Metacognitive serves as the command center or decision-maker when it comes to how people think (Carson, 2021). Those with a greater level of metacognitive cultural intelligence can readily adopt the values, rules, and customs of a certain local culture (Tuan, 2016). People extensively use metacognitive skills, which they can further enhance with training. Metacognition also influences leadership skills, self-awareness, self-control, and monitoring, all of which are associated with leadership (Kontostavlou & Drigas, 2021). On the other hand, Al Banna et al. (2016) define metacognition as the knowledge that people have about their own cognitive abilities and how they control these activities by self-monitoring.

Burcu Duman (2019) found that the metacognition-based teaching practice increased the potential leaders' awareness of their thought processes. However, Norman (2020) argued that metacognition sometimes has a negative impact and isn't always helpful because, for one thing, it can get in the way of doing a job. Second, there are times when the costs of using metacognitive techniques may outweigh their benefits. Third, metacognitive judgments or thoughts that involve a bad self-evaluation can hurt mental health. Most educators do not understand what the word "metacognition" means, which leads to misunderstandings and often poor application. So, it's important to start by making sure that they know and understand key ideas, and that they are familiar with the full range of teaching methods listed above (Dignath & Buttner, 2017; De Smul et al., 2017).

Cognitive

Cognitive cultural intelligence is a specialized understanding of another culture's norms, values, and political, judicial, and economic institutions (Vlajcic et al., 2019). The important function of cognitive flexibility is the ability to generate innovative plans or actions, shifting from tried-and-true methods of problem-solving, to meet the challenges posed by unusual tasks (Bernardo & Presbitero, 2018). Rockstuhl and Van Dyne (2018) conducted a meta-analytic review and found that cognitive and metacognitive CQ, but not motivational or behavioral CQ, can predict intercultural judgment and decision-making. Metacognitive CQ is especially important for the researcher's framework because judgment and decision-making are about choosing between different options while considering the possible outcomes (Starcke & Brand, 2016).

However, Korzilius et al. (2017) emphasized that the subdimensions of cultural intelligence aspects, such as metacognitive, are especially crucial for understanding the cognitive complexity of individuals exposed to diverse and multiple cultures. Furthermore, Yang et al. (2022) found that immigrants' cognitive cultural intelligence (CQ) makes them more aware as business owners. The immigrants' perceptions of the differences in their environments, as well as their sense of global identity, act as positive moderators of the relationship between cognitive CQ and entrepreneurial alertness.

Motivational

The ability to promote efforts to operate in international settings and build interactions with people from different cultures is a motivating factor (Jyoti & Kour, 2015). Organization performance is improved by managers of organizations with high levels of motivational and cultural intelligence (Lorenz et al., 2018). High-motivational individuals are self-assured and eager to engage with others from many cultural backgrounds (Li, 2020). People with a higher motivational CQ were more engaged at work and less burned out on the job. As well as high

motivational CQ helped workers learn about cultural differences that helped them speak up in the right way which had a good effect on work engagement and job stress (Yang, 2023).

The findings of Paparoidamis et al. (2019), revealed that multi-respondent, cross-cultural study has indicated that motivational CQ has a positive moderating impact on perceived service quality and customer devotion in developing markets, the respondents included frontline service personnel as well as customers. Also, Xu and Chen (2017) proposed that expatriates with higher motivational and metacognitive cultural intelligence can engage in multi-cultural settings, which will lead to more creativity at work and they emphasize that motivational CQ and metacognitive CQ are indeed good predictors of cultural learning, which is in turn positively related to cross-cultural job creativity, especially for high-domain learning expatriates.

Behavioral

It is crucial to behave appropriately in a multi-cultural setting (Korzilius et al., 2017). When interacting with people from different backgrounds, one must exhibit both verbal and nonverbal skills. This is known as the behavioral component of cultural capacity (Ang & Van Dyne, 2015). People with high levels of behavioral cultural intelligence are particularly skilled at communicating across cultures (Shaik et al., 2020). Meanwhile, according to Caputo et al. (2018), having the proper verbal and non-verbal skills, including body language and movement expression, is essential for adjusting to a culturally diverse context; it suggests a broad and adaptable threshold for behavior. As a result, communication strategies that work in one cultural context might not work in another (Pratono & Arli, 2020).

Cosain et al. (2022) talked about how motivational and behavioral indicators have a big effect on cultural intelligence and conflict management styles among Lupong Tagapamayapa members, with a p-value of 0.01 for the motivational indicator and a p-value of 0.02 for the behavioral indicator. However, in Türkoğlu's (2022) study, the findings revealed that behavioral cultural intelligence hurts cognitive awareness. On the other hand, metacognitive and motivational cultural intelligence had a positive effect on cognitive flexibility. Nevertheless, there is no correlation between behavioral cultural intelligence and cognitive flexibility, whereas cognitive cultural intelligence has a significant and negative effect on cognitive flexibility.

Conflict Management Styles

In an organizational context, conflict management may play an important role in the overall administration and functioning of the administrator's separate tasks; every civilization contains a widespread element of conflict (Mabunga, R., & Mabunga, M., 2019). Additionally, Caputo et al. (2018) examined the moderating effect of cultural intelligence (CQ) in the relationship between individual cultural orientations and the choice of a conflict management style, finding that cultural intelligence influences conflict management styles in terms of avoiding, forcing, and resolving issues.

Furthermore, the results show that some aspects of cultural intelligence have a moderate effect on the link between a person's cultural intelligence and their conflict management styles. Moreover, Al-Hamdan et al. (2016) attested that there was a negative relationship between the dominating approach of conflict management styles and the nurses' intention to remain in their current positions as caregivers.

Accommodating

A person who takes an accommodating approach put the needs and wants of others before their own. A person will be putting the concerns of others above his/her own and this kind of exchange generally occurs when one side gives in without feeling compelled to do so by the other, there are times when you feel like you are in the wrong, and when you feel like you have no choice but to agree with the other person's point of view (Ang & Van Dyne, 2015). The accommodating individual is more inclined to choose a "middle of the road" perspective when presented with an inevitable disagreement. These people are more likely to avoid the problem head-on by apologizing, making light of it, or expressing their desires in a roundabout way (Benoliel & Barth, 2017). As a method for resolving disagreement, "accommodating" is sometimes referred to as "coordinating" (Khan et al., 2017). By employing the harmonizing strategy, the connection is given significant weight. The agenda contains items of low priority, individuals who wish to look as if they belong to the other side commonly adopt this tactic. When someone consistently employs this method, they will eventually acquire a sense of melancholy since they are always caving in to the other party's requests while sacrificing what is most essential to them (Howell, 2014; Luca, 2021).

Findings from Sahban and Abbas (2018) revealed that the avoiding and compromising styles are generally the most preferred by both Malaysian and Thai employees; accommodating and collaborating are the next preference, followed by competing. Thai employees use more collaborating style rather than Malaysian Employee. While, Competing is preferred by Malaysian workers rather than Thai workers. However, the study of Labrague et al. (2018) on conflict management styles emphasized that when it came to be dealing with and handling conflict, nursing practitioners most frequently utilized the integration approach, followed by the accommodation approach.

Collaborating

The second domain is the collaborating style, which combines assertiveness and cooperation. In solving issues collaboratively, effective interpersonal skills are building blocks that competent leaders can use to provide clarity and accuracy in communications and display a calm and helpful attitude with mutual regard and a genuine understanding of their position as leaders (Minter, 2020).

This method also requires patience and a legitimate procedure. For instance, encroachment conflict resolution strategies should employ a collaborative management approach and mechanisms accepted by relevant parties, permanently resolve the problems, avoid human rights violations, apply international standards, and foster harmonious relationships (Silalahi & Erwin, 2015).

Collaboration is vital in diverse domains of life, employment, and society. The outcome is as follows: Firstly, it improves efficiency by facilitating collaboration among individuals towards a common goal, leading to the effective allocation of resources, time, and effort. When individuals engage in collaboration, they allocate duties based on their respective strengths, leading to expedited and enhanced outcomes (Muindi et al., 2017).

Furthermore, it enhances problem-solving abilities. Collaborating as a team enables individuals to tackle problems from a variety of perspectives and approaches. The variety of problem-solving methodologies might result in holistic solutions that encompass multiple facets of the situation.

Competing

Competing is the third domain in the hierarchy of conflict management techniques. People with a competitive mentality are intimidating and disagreeable, always looking out for number one, even if it means sacrificing others to do it (Dunaetz, 2016). A competitive mindset takes a staunch stance and refuses to accept the perspectives of others. They never stopped arguing for the position or dismissing the viewpoints of others until they got what they wanted (Bao et al., 2016; Peterson, 2004). Employing contradictory techniques may temporarily lessen the intensity of the issue, but it never establishes a final resolution. These competitive tactics are "winning-losing" scenarios where one person exerts pressure on another to change their conduct (Howell, 2014).

Moreover, a study by Hazem et al. (2020) on the effects of various emotional intelligence levels on conflict management strategies reveals that individuals with high levels of emotional intelligence prefer the competing style of conflict resolution more frequently than the other styles. According to Dahshan and Keshk's (2014) research on managers' conflict management styles and their effect on staff nurses, there is a statistically significant negative correlation between attrition intent and competing approaches. However, Boz Semerci (2019), in his research on the relationship between knowledge hiding, conflict, competition, and personal values, discovered that perceived competition did not play a mediating role between conflict types and knowledge hiding.

Avoiding

Reginald (2006) suggested that there are various ways to avoid conflict. This refers to a lack of concern for both oneself and others; the individual in question is interested in avoiding conflict, deferring the issue until a more appropriate occasion, or even withdrawing from the potentially dangerous situation. (Goncalves et al., 2016). This is a conflict management strategy in which an individual fails to adequately handle a disagreement and instead postpones, withdraws, or sidesteps the issue. Most people avoid conflict due to their fear of engaging in an argument or their lack of confidence in their ability to manage disputes (Laoulakou, 2017).

Kayran and Kamil's (2022) study revealed that cultural intelligence has a positive impact on conflict management, while it hurts avoiding, forcing, and career satisfaction. On the other hand, cultural intelligence has a positive impact on avoiding, while cultural metacognition has a positive impact on compromising, yielding, problem-solving, avoiding, and career satisfaction. Furthermore, they found that compromise enhances job satisfaction. Also, the study by Caputo et al. (2018) found that cultural intelligence affects conflict management styles in terms of avoiding, forcing, and resolving issues. Furthermore, their findings show that some parts of cultural intelligence have a moderate effect on the link between a person's cultural intelligence and their conflict management styles.

Compromising

Compromise is the fifth domain of conflict management styles. The compromise approach demonstrates a general concern for oneself and others, and it is a method in which both parties give up something in exchange for something more desirable to them. Also, there is usually no time restriction, and both sides have an equal level of power (Garcia et al., 2018; Gonçalves et al., 2016). Most of the time, the parties agree on a short-term solution that neither of them is completely happy with. This predicament creates a situation that might lead to fresh disputes in the future, and the purpose of this technique is to maintain a certain level of

assertiveness while remaining cooperative to find an expedient, mutually acceptable solution that partially satisfies all parties engaged in the issue (Gonçalves et al., 2016; Myatt, 2019).

People who deal with problems in this way show that they are both fair and practical. Even though this approach may appear to be the "best" way to resolve a disagreement, it often exacerbates the situation, leading to frustration as individuals become accustomed to settling for a small amount but are never able to express satisfaction (Bao et al., 2016). The research by Raykova et al. (2020) found that when medical professionals conflict, they prefer to compromise (7.65 ± 0.10), avoidance (7.44 ± 0.11), and less competition (4.01 ± 0.13). Physicians are more likely to express the behaviors of collaborating and competing, while healthcare professionals prefer avoidance as a strategy of behavior in a conflict situation.

Leadership Skills

This section of the study discussed administrative skills, interpersonal skills, and conceptual skills as the mediating variables of leadership skills and their domains. According to Tannenbaum and Schmidt (2018), leadership skills are defined as the perception of the tools, behaviors, and capabilities that leaders should have in promoting employee well-being and leading to organizational upgradation. The primary job duties of the leaders were to direct and motivate the members towards the implementation of job duties and the achievement of goals and objectives (Stogdill, 2019).

According to Arvey et al. (2017), true leadership skills involve assisting individuals in developing their abilities. Additionally, leaders can achieve success in implementing leadership skills when they assist others in developing their abilities (Lord et al., 2019). The results of the study by Megheirkouni et al. (2018) showed that there are substantial connections between different types of leadership and the skills approach. Furthermore, the study established the necessity of all three approaches, even though the relationship between leadership style and the approach to technical, human, and conceptual abilities varies depending on the degree of management. Rubio and Picardo's (2017) findings revealed no significant correlation between conflict management approaches and leadership skills, between conflict management approaches and management, or, ultimately, between leadership skills and management.

Administrative Skills

To build and maintain a successful early development organization, successful leaders need strong administrative skills (Schulz et al., 2016). Management must possess the necessary administrative skills to meet the organization's objectives as intended (Harris et al., 2019). Administrators at any level need to have good administrative skills. According to the analysis of Özdemir (2020) in his study of the mediating role of perceived administrative support for the effect of job motivation on organizational identification, the subjects did a good job of identifying with the organization and seeing administrative support. The correlation studies showed that the research variables were positively, moderately, and significantly related to each other. The path analysis, on the other hand, showed that the perceived administrative support on the job "partially mediated" the relationship between job motivation and organizational association.

Furthermore, Karakuş (2019) elaborated that when individuals understand that they are receiving administrative support, they experience a sense of self-worth; as a result, their motivation and willingness to manage organizations both increase, and they work even harder to advance the goals of the organization. Workers demonstrate a greater drive for success,

particularly when they receive administrative support, exhibiting increased creativity, courage, and responsibility.

Interpersonal Skills

Effective interpersonal skills are building blocks that competent leaders can use to provide clarity and accuracy in communications, solve issues collaboratively, and display a calm and helpful attitude with mutual regard and a genuine understanding of their position as leaders (Minter, 2020). Also, it is necessary to have well-developed interpersonal skills for all interactions with other people. However, interpersonal skills, such as the ability to truly comprehend others, provide attention, reflect, and listen, are at the foundation of the training that counselors receive (Slovák, 2015).

According to the Rajesh and Suganthi (2016) study on interpersonal communication satisfaction mediation, supervisors should prioritize training in interpersonal communication skills and conducting frequent communication satisfaction audits for followers and subordinates. Interpersonal skills are particularly vital for professionals working in the field of mental health, such as counselors and psychotherapists. Indeed, the counselors' level of interpersonal ability and competence is believed to contribute significantly to the positive impacts. These qualities can be acquired through training, experience, and education (Miller et al., 2015).

Conceptual Skills

Conceptual skills are essential for public officials, and especially for leaders, to make effective managerial decisions that advance overarching goals and navigate the complexities of their organizations. As workers progress through the ranks, their conceptual abilities become more crucial as they are required to offer strategic guidance (Matteson et al., 2016). Most of the time, leaders try to come up with new strategic ideas or important new goals that require everyone in the company to change how they act (Hambrick & Lovelace, 2017). Leadership tasks, such as planning and analysis, have long relied on leaders' ability to conceptualize abstract and complex ideas; however, many leadership and change frameworks lack clarity on the actual significance of leaders' conceptual skills when leading change, in part because conceptualization is often unclear and challenging to understand.

In addition, conceptual skills construct and place an emphasis on an individual's problem-solving abilities and reasoning capacities, both of which are necessary for efficient performance in organizational settings (Ghasemy et al., 2016). More precisely, Latif et al.'s (2021) study results in terms of conceptual skills have important implications for higher education institutions in that creating and sharing knowledge, as well as building capacities, all require certain competencies and skills. Management skills—conceptual, human, and technical— influence the organization's efficacy by 72%, 75%, and 62%, respectively, according to the significance test (Mukarromah et al., 2019).

Correlation between Variables

As showed in the of Ahmad and Saidalavi (2019), cultural intelligence is one of the most important things that determines how successful global leaders are in cross-cultural workplaces. Also, the findings from the Solomon and Steyn (2017) study showed that cultural intelligence is more linked to leadership that gives people choices than to leadership that tells people what to do, and the important factors in motivating leadership included the leader's metacognitive and motivational cultural intelligence. Mohammadi-Khah et al.'s (2020) study

revealed a significant linear relationship and correlation between managers' conflict management strategies and cultural intelligence ($P > 0.001$), signifying a positive and significant relationship between cultural intelligence's understanding aspect and managers' conflict management strategies. Azizi Nejad et al. (2015) conducted a study on the correlation between conflict management styles in medical universities and cultural intelligence. The findings revealed that there was a significant correlation between cultural intelligence and the effectiveness of managers, with a confidence level of 0.95 ($p = 0.011$; $r = 0.288$). There was a significant correlation between motivational and meta-cognitive components of cultural intelligence and managers' effectiveness. Additionally, we found a significant relationship between cultural intelligence and solutions-oriented styles ($p = 0.012$; $r = 0.281$) and control ($p = 0.003$; $r = 0.328$).

The study of Erzen and Armağan (2015) on the effect of leadership on conflict management was examined, and the results of a random effects model's analysis showed that leadership has a small but significant effect on how well people deal with conflicts. However, the study found positive links between nurses' leadership skills, their conflict management strategies, and the extent to which their team assists them. According to Bilgivar and Topal's (2022) study, school leaders mostly preferred the "integration" style and, respectively, "negotiating, compromising, avoiding, and dominating" styles in conflict management. The study revealed a strong positive correlation between the servant leadership style and the integration style of the school principals, a moderate correlation between the compromise and compromise styles, and a weak positive correlation with the avoidance style. The dominance style showed a low negative correlation, while the school principals' servant leadership style positively influenced the integration, negotiation, compromise, and avoidance styles in conflict management.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the study's conceptual paradigm. The paradigm comprises the independent variable, the dependent variable, and the mediating variable. An arrow indicates the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, as well as the relationship between the independent variable and the mediating variable. The study's independent variable, Cultural Intelligence, has four domains, namely, metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral, while the dependent variable, Conflict Management Styles, has five domains, namely, accommodating, collaborating, competing, avoiding, and compromising. The three domains of leadership skills that make up the mediating variable are administrative skills, interpersonal skills, and conceptual skills. We assume that the independent and mediating variables have a causal relationship with conflict management styles.

Snyder's (1974) Self-Monitoring Theory, which asserts that people are either internally or externally motivated, served as the foundation for this study. This theory emphasizes that individuals with cultural intelligence may adjust their behavior according to the nature of the conflict and the requirements of the negotiating process.

During conflict resolution, this shift in behavior in response to specific events is crucial, and the self-monitoring personality trait directly influences an individual's decision to adjust or not (Goncalves et al., 2016). This study was based on the Social Categorization Theory by Turner et al. (1987) and Tajfel (1981), which says that assumptions of dissimilarity and seeing

others as out-group members are what make people react negatively to people from different cultures.

Moreover, this study also used the Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Management Model by Thomas and Kilmann (1974) and Fiedler's Contingency Theory by Fiedler (2015) as cornerstones, supporting the idea that a leader's personality or psychological disposition is a key factor in their ability to lead. Individuals perceive leaders who employ conflict management skills as general strategies or behavioral orientations, offering guidance and direction toward conflict resolution.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework of the Study

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative research design, specifically utilizing a descriptive-correlational approach and a survey-based questionnaire. A descriptive-correlational research strategy focuses on characterizing correlations between variables rather than establishing a causal relationship (Purkait et al., 2014). The chosen methodology is highly appropriate for this study, as the researcher aimed to establish a connection between the mediating impact of leadership skills and the correlation between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles in Lupong Tagapamayapa. By utilizing this approach, the research effectively ascertained the essence of the correlation among the three unique variables. A survey research project entails the collection and analysis of data from a specific Lupong Tagapamayapa to examine a group of individuals or products.

Sampling Design and Technique

The researcher used stratified random sampling to select the respondents. Stratified sampling divides subjects into subgroups called strata based on shared characteristics (Thomas, 2022). As a result, the researcher applied this method since the respondents were only lupong tagapamayapa, who worked in different identified barangays in Malita, Davao Occidental with a total population of 326. To obtain the sample size of lupong tagapamayapa, the researcher used the Slovin formula $n =$ with a 95% level of confidence and a 5% margin of error.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in conformity with ethical standards, following the evaluations and standardized criteria outlined in the study protocol. Throughout the study, the researchers diligently maintained ethical norms to safeguard the responders from any potential injury or misbehavior. The subsequent ethical principles were deliberated upon and strictly followed:

Consent - it was imperative to acquire consent and authorization. Explicit permission was also given to carry out this study. The participants were not forced to take part; instead, if they were unhappy with discussing their experiences with the researcher, they were offered the choice to withdraw.

There was no **conflict of interest** in this case because the researcher's involvement was purely observational and not interactive, thereby maintaining an ethical perspective.

Cultural and Gender Sensitivity: The researcher unambiguously acknowledged and respected the inequalities and differences among the respondents. The researcher did not judge differences as good or bad but strived to understand the differences, inequalities, and varying needs of respondents of all cultural and gender identities from an emic perspective. The person distributing the questionnaire made a clear promise to the respondents to treat their answers with complete confidentiality.

Privacy and confidentiality were strictly enforced. We securely encrypted the data we acquired from the respondents to ensure its confidentiality.

Voluntary Participation: The study provided respondents with the autonomy and freedom to decide whether to participate. We guaranteed the participants that they would not face any form of threat, intimidation, force, or coercion, and that they had the freedom to resign from the research at any point.

DISCUSSION

This chapter provides an exposition of the statistical outcomes, data interpretation, analysis, and pertinent discoveries pertaining to the degree of cultural intelligence, conflict management strategies, and leadership capabilities exhibited by members of Lupong Tagapamayapa. In addition, the correlation analysis between leadership skills and conflict management styles, the significant relationship between leadership skills and cultural intelligence, and the mediating effect of leadership skills on the relationship between leadership skills and conflict management styles at Lupong Tagapamayapa in Malita, Davao Occidental are all examined.

Level of Cultural Intelligence of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Table 1 displays the cultural intelligence level of lupong tagapamayapa members in all barangays of Malita, Davao Occidental. The measurement includes the domains of metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral. Table 1 demonstrates that the metacognitive CQ, which is the initial aspect of cultural intelligence, achieved the highest overall mean score of 4.69 (indicating a very high level). This suggests that the members of the lupong tagapamayapa possess an improved ability to think critically, evaluate, and make decisions when confronted with cultural disparities. They achieve this by utilizing their understanding of cultural diversity, as well as their ability to acquire knowledge and evaluate new cultures. Furthermore, the results suggest that lupong tagapamayapa demonstrates a conscious understanding of the cultural information they utilize while interacting with others

from various cultural backgrounds. Therefore, the findings highlight the importance of metacognitive cultural intelligence (CQ), suggesting that individuals should have the capacity to adapt and modify their behaviors while interacting with conflicting parties who have different cultural ideas.

Individuals who possess a higher level of metacognitive cultural intelligence are more likely to easily embrace the values, rules, and customs of a certain local culture (Tuan, 2016). Metacognitive skills are advanced cognitive abilities that individuals employ extensively and can further enhance via training. Furthermore, metacognition has the potential to influence leadership skills, self-awareness, self-control, and monitoring, all of which are closely linked to leadership (Kontostavlou & Drigas, 2021). According to Al Banna et al. (2016), metacognition refers to individuals' understanding of their own cognitive capabilities and their ability to regulate these processes through self-monitoring. Metacognition pertains to an individual's understanding of their own cultural knowledge while participating in cross-cultural conversations. This approach emphasizes cognitive strategies and intentional information processing, with the goal of assisting individuals in developing mental shortcuts for social interactions across different cultural contexts. Metacognition refers to the process of consciously adjusting one's own cultural norms and behaviors when engaging in cross-cultural interactions by drawing upon several knowledge frameworks to determine the most suitable actions.

Metacognition enhances individuals' capacity to engage in higher-level cognitive processes, such as reasoning, analysis, and decision-making, when encountering cultural differences. They achieve this by increasing their awareness of these mental processes. Through the collective sharing of knowledge, individuals were able to gain a clearer understanding of the diverse cultural variations across the globe. Moreover, it amplifies an individual's ability to acquire knowledge and assess unfamiliar cultures. The capacity of users to be conscious of and observe their own thoughts and actions distinguishes meta-cognitive CQs (De Smul et al., 2017). Conversely, motivational CQ, which is the third domain, had the lowest average score of 4.28 (which is considered very strong) compared to all other domains of cultural intelligence. As a result, we can infer that members of Lupong Tagapamayapa not only possess the ability to effectively carry out their duties in diverse environments, but also demonstrate increased self-assurance and adaptability in settling disputes. This further emphasizes the respondents' preference for interacting with people from diverse ethnic backgrounds. Additionally, motivational, and metacognitive cultural intelligence are strong predictors of cultural comprehension. The cultural intelligence had a high grand mean of 4.48, indicating that members of Luupong Tagapamayapa possess extensive knowledge and acquaintance with the cultures of their constituents. Given that cultural connections largely shape people's lives, we can define cultural intelligence as the ability to navigate and adapt to different cultural environments (Thomas & Van Dyne, 2018). Cultural intelligence enables individuals to effectively navigate diverse cross-cultural situations and readily adjust to varying cultural contexts (Afsar et al., 2019).

Table 1: Level of Cultural Intelligence of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Cultural Intelligence	Mean	SD	Description
Metacognition	4.69	0.5535	Very High
Cognition	4.47	0.6950	Very High
Motivational	4.28	0.7575	Very High
Behavioral	4.49	0.7583	Very High
Overall Mean	4.48	0.6911	Very High

Level of Conflict Management Skills of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Table 2 displays the descriptive findings on the level of conflict management styles among members of the lupong tagapamayapa in Malita, Davao Occidental. We assess these styles in the domains of accommodating, collaborating, competing, avoiding, and compromising. Table 2 reveals that the accommodating domain of conflict management styles received the highest total mean score of 4.71 (excellent) out of the 5 domains. This indicates that members of lupong tagapamayapa make an effort to fulfill the expectations of all parties involved and are willing to adjust to their needs and concerns in order to resolve the conflict through cooperation, consideration, and flexibility, regardless of the nature or behavior of the disputing parties. The results also indicate that the respondents are eager to support the requirements of both parties and provide assistance or guidance in finding mutually advantageous options to explore. The findings support the notion that although the respondents did not receive any personal benefits from the settlement process, they viewed it as essential for resolving the conflict and ensuring peace. According to Benoliel and Barth (2017), individuals can employ the strategy of accommodation by prioritizing the needs of both parties in order to achieve a successful settlement. Furthermore, the implementation of the harmonizing plan accords substantial importance to the relationship.

Furthermore, in the process of settling disputes, the primary aim of lupong tagapamayapa mediation is to facilitate the parties involved in the conflict to come to a mutual agreement on their own accord, rather than imposing a resolution upon them. This enables the conflicting parties to examine the underlying interests that drive their respective viewpoints. This allows the parties to express their opinions and gain a deeper understanding of their grievances. Facilitate the development of a durable and consensual resolution for the parties involved, ensuring that no actions breach the law. This can be achieved by collaborating with both parties collectively and occasionally engaging with them individually (Reynalda et al., 2019). This approach to conflict resolution places significant emphasis on the agenda and the relationship with the other party, with particular attention paid to the former. However, compromise had the lowest average score of 4.58 (excellent) out of 5 categories. This suggests that members of Lupong tend to use a give-and-take approach when trying to resolve issues.

Moreover, they actively strive to promote a compromise between the conflicting parties in order to effectively resolve disputes, discuss their issues, and reach a resolution for the difficulties at hand. Furthermore, the results indicate that the participants actively strive to provide direction to the involved parties in order to achieve a mutually agreeable resolution through discussion, thus addressing the present problem. Typically, the parties reach a temporary resolution that neither of them is entirely satisfied with. This situation could lead to future disagreements. The purpose of this technique is to balance assertiveness and cooperation in order to find a quick and mutually agreeable solution that partially satisfies all parties involved in the matter (Gonçalves et al., 2016; Myatt, 2019).

In addition, this compromising method may be appropriate to employ when the importance of finding a flawless solution is outweighed by the necessity for any solution, when time is limited, when one is facing a deadlock, or when a temporary resolution is urgently required (Bao et al., 2016). Therefore, a moderate level of consideration for both oneself and others distinguishes the compromise method. It refers to a type of negotiation in which both parties make compromises in order to attain their objectives in different domains. Both sides possess equal amounts of power, and there is usually little sense of urgency. The parties often reach a compromise on a temporary solution that does not fully satisfy either party (Gonçalves et al., 2016). This method aims to find a prompt resolution to a problem that is mutually acceptable to

all parties involved while still maintaining their ability to assert themselves and cooperate (Garcia et al., 2018).

Therefore, the conflict management approaches obtain an impressive average score of 4.66 (excellent). This suggests that the members of the lupong constantly improve their conflict management skills and effectively apply them while resolving problems. Van Dyne et al. (2015) highlighted the importance of efficiently handling conflicts in order to promote the efficient functioning of organizations and foster the growth of individuals, cultural members, and society as a whole. Cunha et al. (2016) contended that the act of settling disagreements generally induces greater stress compared to the actual issue at hand. Given that the latter situation is more probable, it is feasible to obtain a benefit in terms of both the willingness to accommodate the other party and the necessity to uphold interests in devising conflict resolution strategies. Hence, possessing the capacity to address and manage the difficulties and apprehensions of fellow community members is imperative for conflict resolution. Proficiency in experience, knowledge, skills, and managerial abilities is necessary in order to effectively address and manage these difficulties and concerns. (Amaresan, 2019).

Table 2: Level of Conflict Management Styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Conflict Management Skills	Mean	SD	Description
Accommodation	4.71	0.5264	Excellent
Collaboration	4.66	0.5863	Excellent
Competing	4.65	0.5977	Excellent
Avoiding	4.68	0.5542	Excellent
Compromising	4.58	0.7554	Excellent
Overall Mean	4.66	0.6040	Excellent

Level of Leadership Skills of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Table 3 presents the descriptive findings of the mediating variable, the leadership abilities of lupong tagapamayapa, in all barangays of Malita, Davao Occidental. We assessed the variable across three domains: administrative skills, interpersonal skills, and conceptual skills. Table 3 reveals that among the three domains of leadership skills, interpersonal skills obtained the highest total mean score of 4.62 (excellent). This suggests that lupong tagapamayapa has essential skills in exchanging thoughts, ideas, feelings, and emotions, which they consistently demonstrate and effectively use during the settlement process. The responders also advocate for cooperation in the activities and suggest using one's emotional energy to inspire and excite others. Effective leaders can employ robust interpersonal skills to assist and facilitate conflict management, resolve disagreements through cooperative methods, and exhibit a composed and supportive demeanor with reciprocal appreciation and true comprehension of their leadership responsibilities. Therefore, competent leaders acknowledge the significance of robust interpersonal abilities (Lopes et al., 2015).

Moreover, possessing well-honed interpersonal skills is crucial for effectively engaging with people in any kind of communication or engagement. This is because it is essential to possess these skills. The core framework of interpersonal skills serves as the foundation for the training that leaders receive. These capabilities encompass, among other aspects, the capacity to understand and share the feelings of others, to engage in attentive listening, and to focus on the content of others' speech (Slovák et al., 2015).

Furthermore, to ensure that the organization's goals are achieved according to the intended plan, management must possess the necessary interpersonal skills. Scholars widely

acknowledge the importance of mediators' interpersonal competence and expertise in achieving beneficial outcomes. Formal learning, practical experience, and theoretical education can acquire these attributes (Miller et al., 2015).

Among all the domains, conceptual skills had the lowest mean score of 4.40 (excellent) in terms of leadership skills. This suggests that the mental abilities and ideas of the lupong tagapamayapa helped the lupon members understand the settlement processes and the organization's value as part of a larger system.

Furthermore, the findings demonstrate that the participants had a high level of proficiency in problem-solving and exhibited adaptability in implementing organizational changes. Mahmood and Baskaran (2022) conducted a phenomenological study that demonstrates the impact of public sector leaders' conceptual skills on their ability to effectively regulate themselves, make sense of situations, demonstrate leadership, and solve problems creatively. The leader assumes the responsibility of establishing efficient leadership and sound organizational protocols that are executed with integrity (Yusuf et al., 2020).

In addition, the leadership skills of the lupong tagapamayapa have a high average score of 4.49 (excellent), indicating that the members of the lupon are highly competent in resolving and managing conflicts. Tannenbaum and Schmidt (2018) defined leadership skills as the discernment of the tools, behaviors, and abilities that leaders must possess to enhance the welfare of individuals and drive organizational change. Leadership abilities are defined as the capacity to lead with effectiveness.

The main responsibilities of the leaders were to provide guidance and inspiration to the organization's members in order to fulfill their work duties and accomplish their aims and objectives (Stogdill, 2019). Arvey et al. (2017) argue that a crucial aspect of good leadership is the capacity to aid others in enhancing their own abilities. Furthermore, leaders will achieve success in implementing leadership qualities if they can facilitate the development of their subordinates' capabilities (Lord et al., 2019).

Table 3: Level of Leadership Skills of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Leadership Skills	Mean	SD	Description
Administrative Skills	4.44	0.6820	Excellent
Interpersonal Skills	4.62	0.6513	Excellent
Conceptual Skills	4.40	0.7477	Excellent
Overall Mean	4.49	0.6936	Excellent

Correlation Analysis between Cultural Intelligence and Conflict Management Styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Table 4 displays the correlation analysis between cultural intelligence and conflict management approaches of lupong tagapamayapa in Malita, Davao Occidental. An r-value quantifies the magnitude of the correlation between two variables, whereas a p-value determines the statistical significance of the connection. The correlation coefficient (r-value) between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles is 0.533, indicating a moderate correlation across all domains. Furthermore, the p-value is $< .001$, which signifies a significant relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles. Therefore, we reject the first null hypothesis.

Tuguz et al. (2015) conducted a study that examined the relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles. The study specifically focused on Jordanian leaders and used data from Jordan to determine the specific aspects of cultural intelligence that have the greatest impact on how these leaders resolve conflicts. The findings of the study revealed a positive correlation between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles among authorities in Jordan. Goncalves et al. (2016) found that cultural intelligence can serve as a reliable indicator for different conflict management strategies employed by leaders. In addition, Hoxha's (2020) study, which focused on organizational leaders, discovered a noteworthy positive correlation between cultural intelligence and different approaches to conflict management. Kayran and Kamil (2022) found that cultural intelligence has a favorable impact on conflict management. In addition, Kim (2020) has shown a favorable correlation between intercultural competence and conflict management in the workplace.

The results also indicate a moderate relationship between different elements of cultural intelligence and the handling of conflicts. Cosain et al. (2022) highlighted the significance of motivational and behavioral factors in influencing cultural intelligence on conflict management styles among members of Lupong Tagapamayapa. The former factor had a p-value of 0.01, while the latter had a p-value of 0.02. Conflict management is critical to the organizational structure because it affects the general administration and the execution of various administrative duties. Although conflict is present in every civilization, certain cultures exhibit superior skills in controlling it compared to others (Mabunga, R., & Mabunga, M., 2019).

Consequently, accomplished global leaders who possess elevated levels of cultural intelligence possess the capability to utilize their worldwide experiences to advance as leaders and enhance the planet for all individuals by implementing the knowledge they have acquired (Ng, 2018). In order for a business to achieve overall success, it is imperative that its employees possess the capacity to effectively handle conflict at both the interpersonal and organizational levels. Consequently, the significance and utility of cultural intelligence in different levels of conflict management have been proven in many forms (Goncalves et al., 2016; Michailova, 2018).

Table 4: Correlation Analysis between Cultural Intelligence and Conflict Management Styles

Particulars	r-value	Description	p-value	Decision
Cultural Intelligence and Conflict Management Styles	0.533	Moderate Correlation	< .001	Reject null hypothesis No.1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlation Analysis between Cultural Intelligence and Leadership Skills of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Table 5 displays the correlation study between cultural intelligence and leadership qualities among members of lupong tagapamayapa in Malita, Davao Occidental. The data presented in Table 5 reveals a strong positive correlation (r-value = 0.637) between cultural intelligence and leadership skills across all domains. Furthermore, the p-value being less than 0.001 indicates a significant relationship between cultural intelligence and leadership skills, leading to the rejection of the second null hypothesis. The findings align with the study conducted by Tong et al. (2015), which showed that effective leadership skills are strongly associated with both cognitive cultural intelligence (CQ) and noncognitive CQ, as well as the education and on-the-job learning acquired. Baker and Delpechitre (2016) emphasized that

possessing cultural intelligence has the potential to enhance leadership abilities, indicating that the importance of cultural intelligence will continue to grow for leaders in today's various cultural environments. They stressed the significance of knowing different cultures for effective participation in global leadership development programs.

In addition, Korzilius et al. (2017) highlighted the importance of cultural intelligence (CQ) and leadership skills in today's diverse and globalized workplaces. Their study revealed a strong correlation between these two factors, emphasizing their essential role in effective leadership. Leadership skills encompass the ability to motivate, support, and direct others in achieving shared objectives, whereas cultural intelligence pertains to the aptitude for effectively engaging with others from diverse cultural backgrounds. Furthermore, Solomon and Steyn (2017) conducted additional research on this subject and discovered that the cultural intelligence of leaders had a stronger correlation with leadership skills that prioritize empowerment rather than directiveness.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis between Cultural Intelligence and Leadership Skills

Particulars	r-value	Description	p-value	Decision
Cultural Intelligence and Leadership Skills	0.637	High Correlation	< .001	Reject null hypothesis No.2

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlation Analysis between Leadership Skills and Conflict Management Styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Table 6 displays the association study between leadership skills and conflict management approaches among members of lupong tagapamayapa in Malita, Davao Occidental. The statistical analysis in Table 6 reveals a significant correlation (r-value = 0.659) between leadership qualities and conflict management styles, indicating a strong relationship across all domains.

Furthermore, the p-value of leadership skills and conflict management styles is less than .001, demonstrating a substantial correlation between leadership skills and conflict management styles. Therefore, we reject the third null hypothesis. Mahel (2021) conducted a study that revealed a high and favorable correlation between leadership qualities and conflict management. Effective conflict management requires strong leadership qualities. These skills enable leaders to effectively address conflicts and foster a positive work environment. Additionally, the techniques used for conflict management can shape perceptions of leadership skills, which in turn impact how individuals view and engage with their leaders.

Furthermore, Moradi et al. (2018) corroborated the results of the present study, demonstrating a robust and favorable correlation between leadership abilities and diverse conflict management strategies. Effective leaders possess the competence to skillfully resolve differences in a way that benefits all parties and advances the achievement of mutually beneficial goals. They create a safe setting for candid dialogue and can uncover the root cause of the problem. Moreover, they can assist in a conflict resolution process that integrates collaboration. In addition, Rukuni et al. (2015) stated that there is a significant correlation between a leader's conflict management style and their level of leadership proficiency.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis between Leadership Skills and Conflict Management Styles

Particulars	r-value	Description	p-value	Decision
Leadership Skills and Conflict Management Skills	0.659	High Correlation	< .001	Reject null hypothesis No.3

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The Mediating Analysis of Leadership Skills in the Relationship of Cultural Intelligence and Conflict Management Styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa

Table 7 presents the mediating analysis of leadership qualities in relation to the lupong tagapamayapa's cultural intelligence and conflict management styles. The study revealed a strong positive correlation between cultural intelligence and leadership qualities, as indicated by a regression coefficient of 0.6858. As the cultural intelligence level of the lupong tagapamayapa improves by one standard deviation, their leadership skills capacity similarly increases by 0.6858. Consistent with this finding, Ahmad and Saidalavi (2019) contended that cultural intelligence plays a crucial role in determining the level of success that global leaders achieve in cross-cultural work environments. Solomon and Steyn's (2017) study reveal a stronger association between cultural intelligence and leadership skills that empower individuals with choices, as opposed to leadership that dictates actions. The key components of effective leadership skills identified in the study identified the leader's metacognitive and motivational cultural intelligence.

In contemporary organizations that are becoming more international and varied, possessing cultural intelligence (CQ) and leadership abilities is crucial for effective leadership. Both of these traits are crucial for effective leadership, as evidenced by the study's findings, which revealed a substantial association between the two. Leadership qualities require the capacity to inspire, empower, and guide others in order to accomplish common goals. Cultural intelligence refers to the ability to effectively engage with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds (Korzilius et al., 2017). Additionally, the findings demonstrated that the leadership abilities of the lupong tagapamayapa had a substantial impact on their approach to resolving conflicts, as indicated by a regression coefficient of 0.4571. Furthermore, we can infer that there is a corresponding increase of 0.4571 in conflict management methods for every 1 standard deviation rise in leadership skills. Mahel (2021) further highlights that there is a strong and positive correlation between leadership qualities and the ability to effectively manage conflict. Proficiency in conflict resolution is essential for good leadership. These abilities enable leaders to effectively manage disagreements and foster a positive work environment. Conversely, conflict management approaches can shape perceptions of leadership abilities, which in turn influence how individuals view and engage with their leaders.

The overall indirect effect is 0.3135, calculated as the multiplication of the effects of cultural intelligence on leadership skills and leadership skills on conflict management styles, with a standard error of 0.0653. Conversely, a regression coefficient of 0.1605, with a standard error of 0.0660, represents the impact of cultural intelligence on lupong tagapamayapa's conflict management techniques. Therefore, we can infer that cultural intelligence significantly influenced the conflict management strategies used by the lupong tagapamayapa. Adding 1 standard deviation to the cultural intelligence level corresponds to a 0.1605 increase in conflict management styles.

Kayran and Kamil's (2022) research demonstrated that cultural intelligence has a favorable impact on conflict management styles. Goncalves et al. (2016) found that cultural intelligence can serve as a reliable indicator for different conflict management strategies employed by leaders. Furthermore, Hoxha's (2020) study, which focused on organizational leaders, discovered a noteworthy positive correlation between cultural intelligence and diverse conflict management strategies. Furthermore, the overall impact has a regression coefficient of 0.4740, which represents the combined influence of both the indirect and direct effects. The indirect impact of 0.3135 shows that leadership qualities mediate about 66.14% of the relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management methods of lupong tagapamayapa. We derive this calculation by dividing 0.3135 by 0.4740 and multiplying the result by 100. The direct impact of cultural intelligence on conflict management approaches is 33.86%, or 34%, calculated as 0.1605 divided by 0.4740 and multiplied by 100.

There is a significant nonzero indirect effect of leadership skills on the relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles, as well as a significant direct effect of cultural intelligence on conflict management styles. This means that the mediation seen in the model is only partly there. This suggests that there exists a substantial correlation not just between the mediating variable and the dependent variable but also a direct correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The Sobel Z-Test was used to assess the significance of leadership skills' mediating influence on the relationship between cultural intelligence (lupong tagapamayapa) and conflict management methods. The results of this test are displayed in Table 12. The fourth null hypothesis is rejected because the p-value falls below the significance level of 0.05. As a result, we can conclude that the influence of leadership qualities on the connection between lupong tagapamayapa's cultural intelligence and conflict management approaches is significant.

Table 7: The Mediating Analysis of Leadership Skills in the Relationship of Cultural Intelligence and Conflict Management Styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa

EFFECT	ESTIMATES	STD. ERROR	LOWER CI	UPPER CI
Indirect Effect	0.3135*	0.0653	0.1986	0.4547
Cultural Intelligence → Leadership Skills	0.6858*	0.0651	0.5574	0.8142
Leadership Skills → Conflict Management Styles	0.4571*	0.0597	0.3393	0.5749
Direct Effect				
Cultural Intelligence → Conflict Management Styles	0.1605*	0.0660	0.0302	0.2909
Total Effect	0.4740*	0.0596	0.3564	0.5917

* $p < 0.05$; SE=Standard Error; CI= Confidence Interval

Figure 2 is the diagram showing the mediating analysis of leadership skills in the relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles of the lupong tagapamayapa. The result of the study revealed that cultural intelligence is a significant predictor of conflict management styles in Luupong Tagapamayapa. Hence, nurturing this variable among members of Luupong Tagapamayapa is important in enhancing conflict management. Further, Luupong Tagapamayapa's leadership skills significantly mediate the relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles. Cultivating leadership skills in conflict management would significantly improve the effect of cultural intelligence on the conflict management styles of Luupong Tagapamayapa. This result is related to the previous study of Cosain et al. (2022) and Gonçalves et al. (2016), which presents the significant relationship between leadership skills, cultural intelligence, and conflict management styles.

Table 8: Summary of Sobel Z-Test

INDIRECT EFFECT	ESTIMATES	SE	P-VALUE	INTERPRETATION
Cultural Intelligence → Leadership Skills	0.6858*	0.0651	<0.001	Significant
Leadership Skills → Conflict Management Styles	0.4571*	0.0597	<0.001	Significant

Figure 2: The Mediating Analysis of Leadership Skills in the Relationship between Cultural Intelligence and Conflict Management Styles of Lupong Tagapamayapa.

SUMMARY

A descriptive-correlational research design was employed in the study and there were one hundred eighty (180) respondents from lupong tagapamayapa in all barangay of Malita, Davao Occidental. The statistical tools that were used are Mean and Standard Deviation, Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation Analysis, and Medgraph using Sobel Z-Test. The overall level of cultural intelligence of lupong tagapamayapa is “Very High” with a grand mean rating of 4.48. This indicates that the members of lupong tagapamayapa have full knowledge and familiarity with the cultures of their constituents. Also, in general, the lupong tagapamayapa’s level of conflict management styles are “Excellent” with a grand mean rating of 4.66 which means that the members of Lupong Tagapamayapa’s conflict management styles are always practiced. While, the overall mean level of leadership skills of lupong tagapamayapa is “excellent” with a grand mean rating of 4.49. This means that the leadership skills of lupong tagapamayapa are very effective.

The correlation analysis of cultural intelligence and conflict management styles has obtained positive correlation coefficient values of 0.533 across all domains and even more convincing is the fact that their p-value is less than 0.001, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the two variables and leads to reject the null hypothesis 1. The correlation analysis reported cultural intelligence and leadership skills have obtained positive correlation coefficient values of 0.637 across all domains and even more convincing is the fact that their p-value is less than 0.001, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the two variables and that leads to reject the null hypothesis 2. The correlation analysis reported that leadership skills and conflict management styles have obtained positive correlation coefficient values of 0.659 across all domains. And that even more convincing is the fact that results

showed that the significance value is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the two variables and that leads to rejecting the null hypothesis 3.

The Mediation Effect Analysis reported that the level of cultural intelligence significantly affects the level of leadership skills with a regression coefficient of 0.6858 with a p-value of less than 0.05. Further, results also showed that lupong tagapamayapa's leadership skills had a significant effect on their conflict management styles with a regression coefficient of 0.4571 with a p-value of less than 0.05. The overall indirect effect is 0.3135 which is the product of the effects of cultural intelligence on leadership skills and leadership skills on the conflict management styles with a standard error of 0.0653. On the other hand, the direct effect of cultural intelligence on the conflict management styles of lupong tagapamayapa has a regression coefficient of 0.1605 with a standard error of 0.0660. This implies that cultural intelligence had a significant effect on the conflict management styles of lupong tagapamayapa. Moreover, the total effect has a regression coefficient of 0.4740 which is the sum of indirect and direct effects. The indirect effect is 0.3135 which means that the mediation of leadership skills to the relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles of lupong tagapamayapa is about 66.14%, which is 0.3135 divided by 0.4740 times 100. On the other hand, the direct effect of cultural intelligence on conflict management styles is 33.86% or 34%, which is 0.1605 divided by 0.4740 times 100. Since the indirect effect of leadership skills on the relationship between cultural intelligence and conflict management styles and the direct effect of cultural intelligence on conflict management styles is nonzero and is significant, we can say that the mediation exhibited in the model is a partial mediation.

In conclusion, the Sobel Z-Test was performed to determine whether the mediation of leadership skills on cultural intelligence and conflict management styles of lupong tagapamayapa should be considered significant. Thus, the fourth null hypothesis is rejected since the p-value is lower than the level of significance, which is 0.05, and it is concluded that the mediating effect of leadership skills on the relationship between Lupong Tagapamayapa's cultural intelligence and conflict management styles is significant.

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